

plots treated with decamethrin at higher than 12 g ai/ha (see table). In Ratna, disease incidence was almost negligible at all concentrations. Cypermethrin equaled carbofuran and 6, 12, 25 g ai/ha decamethrin. Yields in the control were

significantly less than in insecticide-treated plots. The trends in vector population (adults and nymphs) in both cultivars was similar to that of disease incidence.

The conclusion is that 12 g ai/ha of

decamethrin in susceptible TN1 and 6 g ai/ha in tolerant Ratna seem to be the lowest possible doses to reduce disease incidence. *S*

Evaluation of some new synthetic pyrethroids for tungro (RTV) disease and vector control

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Some new synthetic pyrethroids were evaluated against RTV in the field.

Cypermethrin, decamethrin, and carbofuran were included as checks.

Synthetic pyrethroids were sprayed at 10-d intervals from 15 d after transplanting (DT) and to 45 DT. Carbofuran was broadcast at 15-d intervals. Test cultivars were TN1 (susceptible) and Ratna (tolerant). Design was a randomized block in 3- $\times$ 3-m plots with 3 replications for each cultivar. RTV source was artificially induced. Leafhopper population was

recorded at 30 DT, disease incidence at 51 DT, and grain yield at harvest.

Decamethrin + buprofezin (200 g ai/ha), tralomethrin (20 g ai/ha), cypermethrin (50 g ai/ha), and decamethrin (12 g ai/ha) were equally effective in reducing RTV incidence and vector leafhopper populations in cultivar TN1 (see table). In cultivar Ratna, carbofuran and S-423 (1000 g ai/ha) also were effective in reducing RTV incidence and leafhopper population. *S*

Effect of some new synthetic pyrethroids on RTV and vector populations in TN1 and Ratna.^a CRRI, India.

Insecticide	Concentration (g ai/ha)	Disease incidence (%)		Grain yield (t/ha)		Leafhoppers/20 hills at 30 DT			
		TN1	Ratna	TN1	Ratna	TN1		Ratna	
						Adults	Nymphs	Adults	Nymphs
Decamethrin + buprofezin (S-534)	100	42 b	8 bc	0.8 c	3.5 cde	15 ab	11 bc	12 bode	4 ab
	200	20 a	6 ab	1.4 a	4.3 ab	9 a	7 abc	9 abcd	2 a
Tralomethrin (S-528)	10	44 b	10 c	0.8 c	3.7 bcd	19 bc	12 bc	6 abc	7 b
	20	22 a	4 a	1.4 a	4.2 abc	10 a	3 a	5 ab	2 a
S-399	125	100 c	39 f	0.2 e	2.6 f	42 e	91 f	30 g	41 e
	250	96 c	24 e	0.2 e	2.9 ef	42 e	71 ef	19 efg	27 d
S-423	500	97 c	15 d	0.2 e	3.3 def	34 de	23 d	20 fg	13 c
	1000	57 b	8 bc	0.4 d	4.1 abc	30 cde	14 cd	16 def	6 ab
Cypermethrin	50	21 a	4 a	1.5 a	4.3 ab	12 ab	5 ab	3 a	3 ab
Decamethrin	12	20 a	5 a	1.5 a	4.3 ab	12 ab	7 abc	6 abc	3 ab
Carbofuran	2 kg	47 b	11 cd	1.3 b	4.7 a	25 cd	55 e	14 cdef	14 c
Control	-	100 c	42 f	0.2 e	2.9 ef	49 e	120 g	29 g	59 f

^aValues followed by the same letter do not differ significantly at the 5% level.

Relation between rice sheath blight (ShB) and yield

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A generalized relationship between ShB level and yield loss has not been

established across rice-growing environments, mainly because of differences in disease evaluation methods, cultivars used, and disease pressures encountered.

To assess the disease more efficiently, data sets from national reports were analyzed. All data on disease measurement were transformed to

relative lesion height (RLH) (ratio of vertical lesion height of the uppermost leaf or sheath lesion to plant height). Disease severities in scales or range were transformed to mid-RLH values.

Despite divergent environments and different cultivars used, a positive and highly significant linear relationship between RLH of ShB and yield

reduction was obtained (see figure). That linear relationship can be expected under moderate disease pressure.

Although lesions may reach the same height, extent of lesion area may differ with weather conditions.

No significant yield reduction was found when RLH was less than 20%. If lesion reached the 3d sheath from the sheath bearing the flag leaf, and if RLH was about 30%, a significant yield loss was seen.

Additional loss would occur during milling if yield reduction in paddy rice was over 10% (USA data). A 46% yield loss is possible in milled rice if ShB lesion reaches 90% of RLH. $\mathcal{S}$

Relation between relative height of the uppermost ShB lesion and yield reduction in paddy rice (observations from national reports).

Pest Control and Management

INSECTS

Alang-alang gall midge potential as an alternate host for parasitoids

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Alang-alang *Imperata cylindrica* is a natural weed on the dikes of lowland ricefields. The Alang-alang gall midge (AGM) *Orseoliella javanica* Kieffer is its most important insect pest. In hilly and highland regions (altitude: 300-800 m), where the dikes on one side are 1-1.5 m high and 20-40 m long, AGM is abundant, especially where the weed is regularly cut for cattle feed.

Although the rice gall midge (RGM) *Orseolia oryzae* (Wood-Mason) does not attack Alang-alang and the AGM does not attack rice, both belong to the family Cecidomyiidae. Alang-alang with AGM in the RGM habitat does not directly affect RGM. But AGM may be an important alternate host of RGM parasitoids. In mountainous regions, RGM infestation is commonly low.

Six species of hymenopterous parasitoids of RGM have been found in Java and Bali, but only three are important: *Platygaster oryzae* (egg-larval

parasitoid), *Neanastatus oryzae* (pupal parasitoid), and *Propicroscytus mirificus* (syn. *Obtusiclava oryzae*) (larval parasitoid). *P. oryzae* and *N. oryzae* are commonly present in ricefields. Parasitism rates may reach 95% for *P. oryzae* and 50% for *N. oryzae*.

The life cycle of *P. oryzae*, in general, synchronizes with the life cycle of RGM (28-32 d). To study the biology of the RGM parasitoids, 1,032 samples of AGM were taken from 9 locations in West Java during 9 mo in 1983-84. Parasitoids, particularly larval and

1. Fluctuation of Alang-alang GM and its parasitoids in 7 locations in West Java, Jul 1983-Mar 1984. Figures above the columns indicate number of silvershoots taken in 1 h of monthly sampling time.